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Comparative analysis of product and network supply chain resilience

Dmitry Ivanov*

Department of Business Administration, Berlin School of Economics and Law, Badensche Str. 50, 10825, Berlin, Germany
E-mail: divanov@hwr-berlin.de [Ivanov]

Abstract

Supply chain resilience has been extensively investigated at the network and firm levels. More granular studies at the level of product supply chain resilience are scarce. In this paper, we examine relationships between product supply chain resilience, firm resilience, and network resilience. We simulate supply chains with two products in different settings of structural and process diversity, connectivity, and flexibility. The methodology is based on discrete-event simulation. The focus of the analysis is on managerial insights. Our main insights show that the resilience of product supply chains depends on the firm and network resilience, and higher firm and network resilience do not always automatically translate into higher resilience at the product level. Managerial implications are discussed and generalized. The outcomes of our study can be used by supply chain and operations managers to improve the resilience of supply chain with consideration of both product and network levels. We contribute to the literature by offering novel insights on the interrelations between firm and network resilience practices and product supply chain resilience.

Keywords: supply chain resilience; simulation; performance

1. Introduction

Supply chain resilience became of utmost importance for companies because of the increasing frequency of disruptions and long-term vulnerabilities triggered by the pandemic, semiconductor shortages, and geopolitical tensions (Dotoli et al., 2016; Sawik, 2021; Jeihoonian et al., 2022; Dubey et al., 2023; Hägele et al., 2023). While the broad and growing interest in supply chain resilience among practitioners became visible after the COVID-19 pandemic, the research community started developing the associated body of knowledge long before the pandemic disruptions (Blackhurst et al., 2005; Sheffi and Rice, 2005; Bode et al., 2011; Dubey et al., 2021a; Jin et al., 2024). The proposed resilience capabilities, modeling, and measurement techniques have helped supply chain managers to improve resilience and start preparing for resilience-centric supply chain

*Corresponding author.

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management (Pettit et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2016; Li et al., 2017; Dubey et al., 2021b; Iftikhar et al., 2021; Ivanov, 2021; Li et al., 2022a, Brusset et al., 2023; Lee and Moon, 2024; Li et al., 2023).

In generalized terms, resilience has been mostly considered at the network and firm levels. At the network level, the overall value-adding systems comprising suppliers, factories, distribution centers (DCs), and customers have been studied with the objective to increase their total resilience (Wang et al., 2017; Hosseini et al., 2019; Dolgui et al., 2020; Ivanov and Rozhkov, 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Namdar et al., 2021; Aldrighetti et al., 2023; Li et al., 2024). Resilience of firm supply chains has also been examined focusing on developing internal and external resilience capabilities (Brusset and Teller, 2017; Li et al., 2021; Lücker et al., 2021; Wang and Sun, 2021; Li et al., 2022b; Li et al., 2022c).

At a more granular level of analysis, it can become necessary to analyze product supply chain resilience. Consider an example. Sony's Play Station supply chain became prone to disruptions in the semiconductor supply chains because of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. The reduced resilience has translated into sales decreases and product shortages in 2021 and 2022. It took Sony three years until the end of 2023 to recover and completely fix its Play Station supply chain worldwide (BBC, 2023). Interestingly, other product supply chains of Sony have not lost their resilience to the extent of the Play Station's one.

Relationships between product supply chain resilience, firm resilience, and network resilience still represent a research gap that this study aims to address. Our objective is to examine dependencies and differences in the resilience of product, firm, and network supply chains. We proceed as follows. We simulate the supply chains of two products in different settings of structural and process diversity, connectivity, and flexibility. In particular, we test resilience for three different settings of networks, that is, linear supply chains, full flexibility, and a mix of both. These three settings are in line with extant literature (Sethi and Sethi, 1990; Simchi-Levi and Wei, 2012; Simchi-Levi et al., 2018; Shen et al., 2019), which provided evidence about relationships between different flexibility degrees and system robustness. In the context of this research, we consider full flexibility as maximum network variety and connectivity.

We contribute to the literature by offering novel insights on the interrelations between firm and network resilience practices and product supply chain resilience. Our main insights show that the resilience of product supply chains depends on the firm and network resilience, and higher firm and network resilience do not always automatically translate into higher resilience at the product level. Managerial implications are discussed and generalized.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. In Section 2, a literature review on the related research streams is presented. Section 3 introduces the modeling setup. Experimental results are explained in Section 4. Section 5 is devoted to a sensitivity analysis while Section 6 is a discussion of managerial implications. We conclude in Section 7 with a summary of major results and outlining future research areas.

2. Literature review

We build on and contribute to two research streams, namely, measurement of supply chain resilience and resilience simulation. We organize our literature review accordingly.

2.1. Measuring supply chain resilience

In order to measure the impact of disruptions on supply chains, several approaches have been introduced, aiming at resilience quantification. In general, three groups of methods can be classified, that is, indirect resilience measurement through supply chain performance indicators, indirect resilience measurement through graph-theoretical metrics, and direct resilience measurement through specific resilience indicators.

In the first group, deviations in on-time delivery (OTD), fill rate, annual sales and revenues have been usually translated into resilience quantification (Burgos and Ivanov, 2021; Ivanov, 2022b; Timperio et al., 2022; Lukinskiy et al., 2023). For example, Singh et al. (2021) and Ivanov (2020) use OTD (i.e., a ratio of on-time delivered orders to the total number of orders placed) as an indicator of resilience. The larger the deviation from the planned values, the lower the resilience.

In the second group, methods of network theory are used to measure supply chain resilience. Such metrics as degree and betweenness centrality, connectivity, and reachability coefficients have been used to quantify structural integrity, connectivity, and flexibility (Wagner and Neshat, 2010; Kim et al., 2015; Osadchiy et al., 2016; Sokolov et al., 2016; Pavlov et al., 2018; Ivanov and Sokolov, 2019; Bier et al., 2020; Li and Zobel, 2020; Li et al., 2020). Besides, entropy and Bayesian networks have been used to quantify resilience based on network adaptability and failure perspectives, respectively (Ivanov and Arkhipov, 2011; Hosseini and Ivanov, 2020, 2022).

The third group's methods are based on measuring the intensity of performance loss and recovery (Torabi et al., 2015; Zobel et al., 2021). Focusing on recovery time and the time a supply chain is able to cope with shortages, Simchi-Levi et al. (2015) measured resilience using supplier risk exposure. They introduced two indicators, that is, time-to-recover and time-to-survive. Time-to-recover measures the period between a disruption-driven capacity shutdown and the recovery of original capacity or its substitution by a back-up source. Time-to-survive shows how long a supply chain can operate without its disrupted capacity (e.g., using some pre-positioned inventory). In short, if time-to-survive is longer than time-to-recover, a supply chain is considered resilient. However, there is no explicit quantification of resilience in this method. Quantification of resilience was proposed in Torabi et al. (2015) and Zobel et al. (2021) based on shortages and recovery time. Hosseini and Ivanov (2020, 2022) quantified resilience using Bayesian networks. Mosayebi et al (2024) analyzed time-to-adapt as the duration from the decision to adapt to the point when the new, modified process is operational. However, none of these studies have analyzed resilience at the product supply chain level. The relationships between the product, firm, and network resilience also remained unexplored.

2.2. Simulation

Simulation is a favorable methodology for the analysis of both structural and flow dynamics (Carvalho et al., 2012; Schmitt et al., 2017; Macdonald et al., 2018; Stewart and Ivanov, 2022; Jackson et al., 2024). Simulation became one of the central methodologies to study supply chain resilience (Llaguno et al., 2022; Ivanov, 2023a; Saisridhar et al., 2024). Different simulation methods such as system dynamics (Ghadge et al., 2022), agent-based modeling (Rozhkov et al., 2022), and discrete-event simulation (Ivanov, 2022b) have been used for the analysis of dynamic impacts

Fig. 1. System setup.

of disruptions and supply chain resilience stress-testing for singular disruptions, ripple effect, and long-term crises.

In this paper, we use anyLogistix supply chain simulation and optimization software. Its AnyLogic-based simulation engine and performance visualization tool allow combining predictive and descriptive analytics to conduct rigorous scientific research. anyLogistix has been extensively used in studies on supply chain resilience and stress testing (Ivanov, 2017; Ivanov, 2019; Dolgui et al., 2020; Burgos and Ivanov, 2021). One of the most known papers on using anyLogistix for disruption impact prediction is the one of Ivanov (2020) devoted to the prediction of COVID-19 pandemic impacts on global supply chains. Ivanov and Das (2020), Moosavi and Hosseini (2021), and Singh et al. (2021) are other examples of using anyLogistix to predict the effects of disruptions on supply chain performance. Stewart and Ivanov (2022) and Timperio et al. (2022) used anyLogistix to develop a decision-support framework for supply chain resilience, and Ivanov (2023a) showed how anyLogistix can be used for building intelligent digital supply chain twins and a decision-support system for supply chain resilience stress-tests. To summarize, recent publications provide strong evidence that anyLogistix can be successfully used for simulation, optimization, and performance visualization of supply chain performance and dynamic behaviors to perform different stress tests, recovery, and resilience analyses.

In summary, structural diversity, flexibility at the process and product levels, and identification of critical nodes and links have been indicated in the literature as the main factors influencing resilience. Adaptive networks can exhibit higher resilience because they can accommodate dynamic changes in connectivity, that is, they exhibit structural dynamics (Ivanov, 2018; Demirel et al., 2019; Ivanov and Dolgui, 2020; Chauhan et al., 2021; Dolgui et al., 2024). We build on these observations when designing our simulation scenarios.

3. Model setup

We consider a system with two homogenous, non-substitutable products, a firm supply chain consisting of two DCs and two markets (customers), and a supply chain network consisting of the firm supply chain and suppliers (factories) (Fig. 1).

We consider two products—A and B—with two specific, non-substitutable markets. The product flow settings described above are depicted in Fig. 2.

Setting 1:

Setting 2:

Setting 3:

Fig. 2. Product flow settings.

In Fig. 2, object “Customer” represents the product market A while the object “Customer2” represents the market for product B. We are interested in examining three distinct settings. In the first setting, each of the two products has its dedicated supply chain, that is, one factory, one DC, and one customer. Object “Factory” produces product A, while object “Factory2” produces product B. In the second setting, there is full flexibility so that each factory can produce each product and any path in the network can ship both products without any capacity constraints. The third setting is similar to the second one, but there is only one factory for the production of both A and B, which is a common supplier for both DCs.

The motivation for the examination of these particular settings stems from literature. The first setting is a traditional linear supply chain system widely studied in resilience research (Babai et al.,

2023; Aldrighetti et al., 2024). The second setting reflects the case of full flexibility in the supply chain in line with (Dolgui et al., 2018; Chopra et al., 2021; Ivanov, 2023b). The third setting represents the case of a single source, which is considered a critical supplier at the intersection of two product supply chains (Ivanov, 2022a; Kosasih and Brintrup, 2022; Ivanov et al., 2023). We stress that the simplicity of the systems considered is motivated by the main objective of this paper, that is, to obtain managerial insights on how product resilience is interrelated to product and network resilience. In preparing this paper, we run several, much more complex scenarios and obtained the same managerial insights as the simple systems. As such, we prefer to explain our ideas in this paper using simple systems since this allows for their better understanding and explanation of the insights.

A discrete-event simulation model has been built in anyLogistix supply chain simulation and optimization software. anyLogistix has been widely considered as a reliable tool for the simulation of supply chain resilience and dynamic behaviors (Ivanov, 2023b). Some essential benefits of anyLogistix for supply chain resilience modeling include the ability to create comprehensive discrete-event simulation models, incorporating industry-specific sourcing, inventory, production, and transportation control policies as well as performance indicators. anyLogistix facilitates the visualization and analysis of structure, flow, and performance in dynamic settings, making it an ideal tool for time-dependent, event-driven, and impact-oriented analyses, which are critical for supply chain resilience and stress testing. Moreover, by combining optimization and simulation models with external data sourcing and performance evaluation tools, anyLogistix serves as a core platform for building digital twins of supply chains. One drawback of using anyLogistix in research is its black-box nature and the limited number of pre-programmed control policies. However, these limitations can be addressed through integration and process customization in AnyLogic.

The following major settings and assumptions have been included in the model. Demand is modeled in a deterministic manner to avoid operational vulnerability in the system, which might be over-crossed by disruption-based variability. Customer orders are generated every five days with 10 product units per order. DC and factories operate a continuous review inventory control policy with a re-order point of 10 units and a target inventory of 20 units. No extra risk mitigation inventory in the supply chain is considered. The lead time between the factory and DC is two days and between DC and customers –1 day. The expected lead time (ELT) for the customers (i.e., the time between new order placement and fulfillment of this order) is five days. Production and transportation capacity is unconstrained. Less-Than-Truckload (LTL) transportation policy and dynamic sourcing policy (i.e., a flexible change of a product source in case of a disruption) are used. Backordering is allowed. Production capacity at factories is unlimited. A simulation period of 365 days is considered.

The resilience is measured by the ELT service level which is OTD quantified as a ratio of customer orders delivered on time to all orders placed by the customers (Equation 1).

$$OTD = \frac{\text{number of on - time orders}}{\text{total number of orders placed}} \quad (1)$$

An order is considered to be on-time if it is delivered within the ELT. The usage of the ELT service level as a resilience indicator is motivated by the extant literature (Singh et al., 2021; Ivanov, 2022b). We note that in anyLogistix, ELT service level counts statistics related only to the order delivery

Table 1
Expected lead time (ELT) service level (on-time delivery [OTD]), in %

Experimental settings	Total for both products A and B	Product A	Product B
1	95.9	91.8	100
2	100	100	100
3	94.5	94.5	94.5

phase. The real order fulfilment time (i.e., a time between order generation and order delivery) can be longer because of possible waiting time due to a disruption (i.e., a backlog).

4. Experiments

The experiments have been run according to the following logic, which aligns with the extant literature on simulation modeling of supply chain resilience and stress testing (Ivanov, 2020; Burgos and Ivanov, 2021; Ivanov and Dolgui, 2022a). First, nominal scenarios (i.e., business as usual, disruption-free) have been studied to validate the correctness of the model and create a benchmark for the resilience metric to be considered in the disruption scenarios. As expected, the OTD in the disruption-free scenarios for all three settings is 100% since no other vulnerabilities and uncertainties (e.g., demand and lead-time fluctuations) exist in the modelling setting. This is done in the interest of a clear focus on the impact of disruptions without mixing them with other operational vulnerabilities.

Second, disruption scenarios have been run. For all three settings, two disruptions at the object “Factory” have been considered, each lasting 25 days. The first disruption happened on day #100, and the second disruption occurred on day #200. The disruption scenarios considered are shown in Fig. 3.

The simulation results are summarized in Table 1 and illustrated in Figs 4–6.

The values of the ELT service level (i.e., the OTD) shown in Table 1 are measured at the end of the simulation experiment (i.e., at day #365).

It can be observed in Table 1 and Figs. 4–6 that different settings for the product supply chain exhibit different resilience. In the first setting (Fig. 4), two products have dedicated supply chains that do not intersect. In case of factory disruptions, only the performance of the supply chain for product A is adversely affected decreasing by 8.2%. The OTD of the product B remained at 100%, and the total OTD for the network dropped to 95.9%. We note that the recovery process visualization in Figs. 4 and 6 is non-linear since average values of the ELT service level are presented in the diagrams at each point of time.

In the second and third settings, identical values for both products A and B separately, and in their totality, respectively. As expected, setting #2 (i.e., full flexibility) results in 100% OTD so that the supply chains of both products A and B, and the network as a whole can be considered resilient. The resilience comes about using the possibility to produce product A at the factory #2 (object Factory2) during the disruption at the primary supplier of the product A (i.e., object Factory). In the third setting, there is a drop in the OTD to 91.8% for both products A and B separately, and the

Fig. 3. Disruption scenarios.

network in total. This can be explained by the existence of a critical supplier (i.e., object Factory), which produces both A and B, along with the absence of alternative suppliers and extra inventory in the system.

5. Sensitivity analysis

In this section, we present the results of a sensitivity analysis regarding an extended structural design, which involves adding an additional factory (Factory 3), a new DC (DC3), and a new customer (Customer 3) with a demand for product A identical to that of Customer 1 (Fig. 7).

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Fig. 4. On-time delivery (OTD) for products A, B, and total in the Setting 1

Factory 3 is capable of producing both product A and product B in Settings 2 and 3, whereas in Setting 1, it produces only product A. These designs have been utilized in the existing literature (Simchi-Levi et al., 2018; Shen et al., 2019).

We conducted simulations for the extended Settings 1–3 under the same disruption scenario described in Section 4. The results are summarized in Table 2.

A comparison of the initial and extended analyses reveals similar trends and demonstrates the model's sensitivity to changes in structures and demand. As shown in Table 2, the results are responsive to structural changes. As expected, in Setting 2 (full flexibility), the OTD performance remains unchanged. This outcome is not surprising, given that no constraints on production or logistics capacities are considered, and Customer 3 shares the same demand pattern as Customer

Fig. 5. OTD for both products A and B in the Setting 2

Fig. 6. OTD for both products A and B in Setting 3

Table 2
ELT service level (OTD) for initial and extended Cases 1–3, in %

Experimental settings	Total for both products A and B		Product A		Product B	
	Initial structure (Fig. 3)	Extended structure (Fig. 7)	Initial structure (Fig. 3)	Extended structure (Fig. 7)	Initial structure (Fig. 3)	Extended structure (Fig. 7)
1	95.9	97.3	91.8	95.9	100	100
2	100	100	100	100	100	100
3	94.5	96.3	94.5	96.9	94.5	95.9

1. In settings 1 and 3, however, we observe a positive impact of adding another market for product A, which improves the OTD due to higher total and on-time fulfilled demands for product A. This indicates that sensitivity to network design is influenced more by the parameters of material flows (e.g., demand, capacity, and inventory) than by structural changes alone.

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Fig. 7. Extended structural Settings 1–3 for sensitivity analysis.

Table 3
Major simulation results and their managerial implications

Simulation settings	Simulation results	Managerial implications	Recommendations
1	A factory disruption in the product A supply chain impacts only the performance of the supply chain for product A. The OTD of product A is drops by 8.2%. The OTD of the product B remains 100%, and the total OTD for the network drops to 95.9%	Dedicated supply chains for different products positively influence network resilience and partially product resilience	If technologically impossible or economically infeasible to implement full flexibility, different product supply chains should have widely independent structures to avoid the ripple effects across different products
2	Full flexibility results in 100% OTD for both products A and B and the network as a whole	The supply chains of both products A and B and the network as a whole can be considered resilient	If technologically possible and economically feasible, supply chain networks should be built on the principles of structural variety and process flexibility to ensure adaptability
3	There is a drop in the OTD to 91.8% for both products A and B separately, and the network in total	Intersections of product supply chains at critical nodes or links have an adverse effect on both network and product resilience. Even the full flexibility in the firm supply chain does not help to recover and ensure resilience if a disruption happens upstream (i.e., at a factory)	The existence of critical suppliers prone to disruptions at the intersections of different product supply chains should be avoided or compensated by some extra inventory in the supply chain network

6. Managerial insights

In this section, we discuss the numerical results obtained through simulation in light of their managerial insights. Table 3 summarizes major simulation results and their managerial implications.

We now elaborate on the individual insights.

Insight 1: Full flexibility increases resilience both at the product and network levels. This insight aligns with the existing literature pointing to the primary role of flexibility and adaptability in resilience (Ivanov, 2022a; Ivanov and Dolgui, 2022b; Alikhani et al., 2023; Sodhi et al., 2023). Indeed, the possibility of producing different products at different factories (e.g., through flexible manufacturing systems and 3D printing) allows for increased product resilience. In turn, the product resilience translates into the network resilience as observed in setting #2.

Insight 2: Dedicated supply chains for different products positively influence network resilience and partially product resilience. Suppose different products in the supply chain follow dedicated paths. In that case, this is favorable for both overall network resilience and resilience of products that are not concerned with the disrupted nodes or links. This can be observed through setting #1. If

full flexibility is impossible, then dedicated supply chains for different products can be instructive. In case of a disruption in one product supply chain, other products will not be affected. The ripple effects will also not cascade across different products (Hosseini et al., 2020; Habibi et al., 2023). The downside of this strategy is the missing flexibility and adaptability (Ivanov, 2024).

Insight 3: Intersections of product supply chains at critical nodes or links hurt both network and product resilience. As observed through setting #3, two product supply chains intersect at a critical supplier, which is subject to disruptions. Even the full flexibility in the firm supply chain does not help to recover and ensure resilience at the network and product levels if a disruption happens upstream (i.e., at a factory). This observation can be instructive for the analysis of critical nodes and links in the supply chain networks to ensure the resilience of individual products (Kosasih and Brintrup, 2022).

Insight 4: Indicators of supply chain resilience at the network level do not always inform about product resilience. One should be careful with judging about supply chain resilience based on aggregate network indicators. This might lead to a situation when problems with the resilience of some products may remain hidden. As shown in setting #1, the average value of the OTD indicator neglects the problems with the resilience of product A. As such, the analysis of the network resilience should be supplemented with the product supply chain resilience analysis. This is a new indication that has yet to receive proper attention in literature.

Returning to our motivating example of Sony's supply chains, our study can help explain some industry effects and provide practical recommendations. First, Sony could have mitigated issues with the PlayStation supply chain by enhancing the resilience and flexibility of their supplier base. This includes considering intersections with other Sony product supply chains, potential component sharing across different products, and rerouting material flows. Second, a combination of technological standardization and supplier diversification could improve resilience by increasing flexibility through inventory sharing and greater network variety.

7. Conclusion

The central motivation for this study was the analysis of interrelations between supply chain resilience at the product, firm, and network levels. This motivation stems from numerous practical examples of the same firm experiencing different resilience for different products. Our objective was to examine how different settings of supply chain resilience at the firm and network levels translate into product supply chain resilience, and vice versa.

For analysis, we considered a system with two homogenous, non-substitutable products, a firm supply chain consisting of two DCs and two markets (customers), and a supply chain network consisting of the firm supply chain and suppliers (factories). Being simple and concise in its setup, this system allowed us to deduce novel and interesting managerial insights, which we also observed in modeling much more complex systems. The system used allows us to explain these insights more clearly and concisely as we would with a complex system analysis.

anyLogistix supply chain software has been built with a discrete-event simulation model that is widely used to simulate resilience and dynamic behaviors. We simulated supply chains with two products in three distinct settings of structural and process diversity, connectivity, and flexibility: linear supply chains, full flexibility, and partial intersections of linear supply chains.

Our main conclusions are as follows. The resilience of product supply chains depends on the firm and network resilience, and higher firm and network resilience do not always automatically translate into higher resilience at the product level. Full flexibility resilience practices increase resilience both at the product and network levels. This insight points to the primary role of flexibility and adaptability in resilience, which can be achieved, for example, through flexible manufacturing systems and 3D printing. Dedicated supply chains for different products positively influence network resilience and partially product resilience. If different products in the supply chain follow separated, non-intersecting material flow paths, this is favorable for products that are not concerned with the disrupted nodes or links. Total network resilience would also benefit from such a setting because of the absence of critical nodes (i.e., common suppliers prone to disruptions). This resilience practice is recommendable if full flexibility is impossible from technology or logistics perspectives. Most critical network designs are those with intersections of different product supply chains at critical nodes or links, which adversely affects both network and product resilience. Even the full flexibility in the firm supply chain does not help to recover and ensure resilience at the network and product levels if a disruption happens at the critical nodes upstream (i.e., at a factory). This observation can be instructive for analysis of critical nodes and links in the supply chain networks to ensure the resilience of individual products.

Finally, we observed that indicators of supply chain resilience at the network level do not always inform about product resilience. As such, it can be instructive to be careful with judging about supply chain resilience based on aggregate network indicators. This might lead to wrong estimations about the resilience of some products. Network resilience should be supplemented with the product supply chain resilience analysis. This is a new indication that has not yet received proper attention in the literature.

Our results and conclusions—as with any research—are subject to limitations that are primarily related to the methodology and scope of the work and lead us to articulation of future research areas. We examined only three possible network designs. Other resilience practices such as risk mitigation inventory and capacity reservations could be examined in future. We assumed that production capacity at factories is unlimited, and DCs can process all the inventory arriving from the factories in disruption cases. In reality, the potential of using full flexibility can be reduced by limited manufacturing, shipment, and warehousing capacities as noted by Simchi-Levi et al. (2018). While simulation is a powerful method to study supply chain dynamics, we call for other methodologies based on optimization and network theory methods in a further examination of the relations between resilience at the product, firm, and network levels. We focused on the operational and customer performance assessment (through DR and OTD, respectively). Future research can consider financial performance as well, for example, addressing a trade-off of resilience versus efficiency (Chopra et al., 2021; Ivanov, 2022a; Aldrighetti et al., 2023; Proselkov et al., 2024). Finally, complexity of the systems for analysis can be increased, which—in combination with different methodologies and resilience practices—might potentially lead to novel managerial and theoretical implications.

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